

Prognosis of patients with post-Covid-19 condition: Prospective cohort cluster analysis at one year

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ABSTRACT

Objective: We aimed to identify clinically relevant clusters among patients with post-Covid-19 condition (PCC) and assess prognosis overall and within clusters.

Methods: Prospective cohort study of patients with PCC attending a rehabilitation clinic. We monitored patient reported outcome measures (PROMs): EuroHIS quality of life and symptoms. Unsupervised hierarchical cluster analyses were performed to identify clusters of patients with different quantity of symptoms, and symptoms presenting together. Preliminary findings on symptom prevalence and quality of life at 12 months are reported. **Results:** Among 409 patients, 70.4% were women, with an average baseline of 20.3 (SD 6.8) symptoms. Three clusters emerged based on symptom quantity, labelled by the average number of symptoms at baseline: Cluster-11 (17% of all patients), Cluster-17 (35%), and Cluster-25 (48%). Multinomial logistic regression showed female sex, multiple comorbidities predicting more symptoms. Four symptom-based clusters were defined: fatigue and cognitive complaints; pain, trouble sleeping, palpitations and other symptoms; gastrointestinal symptoms; and emotion-related symptoms. Linear regression models showed that female sex, multiple comorbidities, anxiety, use of antidepressants, BMI and smoking were among the determinants of symptom clusters. In 12-month follow-up, symptom count decreased, and quality of life improved across all clusters, with 9% having good quality of life at baseline and 33% at 12 months.

Conclusion: Four patient clusters based on symptoms were identified in the PCC cohort. Prognosis was favorable across all clusters, with symptom reduction and improved quality of life observed. Female sex, comorbidities, BMI, and mental-health related variables predicted higher symptom burden, suggesting multifactorial origins of PCC.

1. Introduction

After a Covid-19 infection, up to 13% of patients suffer from long-term symptoms known as post-acute sequelae of SARS-CoV-2 infection, long Covid or post-Covid-19 condition (PCC) [1,2]. The exact mechanisms and causal pathways of long-term symptoms are still unclear. The syndrome seems heterogeneous, and several factors probably contribute to the emergence of the condition [3,4]. Most of the published cohorts on the prognosis of post-Covid-19 condition concern hospitalized patients in the acute phase [5–8]. Whilst some patients recover, prognosis has not been well described, and little is known on recovery in different clusters of patients with PCC.

To get a better understanding of the post-Covid-19 condition, it may help to identify both different patient and symptom clusters included in

the condition. Post-Covid-19 condition symptom clusters have been studied, especially in materials concerning hospitalized patients [9–14]. So far, there are less studies conducted on outpatients, and information on outcomes in different patient clusters is much needed. On top of this, clinicians and patients need information about prognosis.

To assure effective treatments, it will help to understand the different clusters, as each may have different causal pathways resulting in the symptoms. Often the PCC has been approached from a purely medical model, attempting to find individual biomechanistic explanations. The clusters might help to better understand the complexities of post-Covid-19 condition: that it is heterogeneous, most likely multifactorial and probably better explained by the biopsychosocial model [15–17], like pain [18].

In a prognostic study of one year follow-up, we aimed to find

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clinically meaningful subgroups for patients with PCC, which in the acute phase were mostly treated as outpatients in a tertiary care clinic. For assessment of overall and subgroup specific prognosis, we utilized a wide spectrum of patient-reported outcome measures, quality of life and symptoms. This study reports preliminary findings of this prospective cohort which is still ongoing.

2. Methods

2.1. Study design and patient cohort

We conducted a prospective, single-site cohort study consisting of administering questionnaires and clinical examinations to adult patients referred to the Clinic for Long-Term Effects of COVID-19 at Helsinki University Hospital (HUS). The referrals come from health care units within HUS and other hospital districts during years 2021–2023. The patients with lung abnormalities were not referred our clinic but to pulmonary medicine. In addition, there is a specific rehabilitation clinic at HUS for patients having problems after intensive care unit (ICU) treatment.

All admitted patients have had confirmed COVID-19. This rehabilitation clinic is the only one founded for patients with PCC in Finland, and the setting is at the level of a university hospital tertiary care.

Inclusion criteria were age ≥ 18 years, referred to the Clinic for Long-Term Effects of COVID-19 either from other hospital units or primary care, COVID-19 diagnosis ≥ 3 months earlier (confirmed by PCR or antigen testing), and willingness to be enrolled in the study, by signing the informed consent. Since PCR testing became rare in 2023, we then also accepted antigen testing.

Exclusion criteria were patients not able to fill out the forms in Finnish and participation in the study would be unreasonably inconvenient (e.g., patients in bed rest).

Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) questionnaires were sent to patients within a week before or at their first visit to the clinic and then at 3, 6, and 12 months afterwards. The questionnaires included quality of life measured by European Health Interview Survey-Quality of Life (EUROHIS-8) index with eight questions (overall quality of life, general health, energy, daily living activity, self-esteem, social relationships, finances, and home) [19]. Each item is scored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (very dissatisfied) to 5 (very satisfied) and a higher total score (1–5) on all items indicates a higher quality of life.

Patients were also asked to circle the symptoms present during the last three months in a 35-symptom table, including five typical symptoms in seven domains: cardiopulmonary, gastrointestinal, muscles and joints, general symptoms, and depressive, nervous, and cognitive reactions. This table is based on the Danish Bodily Distress Syndrome (BDS) checklist and is a tool for clinicians to identify the spectrum of patients' symptoms [20]. It covers the outcomes presented in the core set of outcomes (COS) for PCC [21]. We repeated the symptom assessment at 3, 6 and 12 months. As a surrogate for recovery, we used quality of life EuroHIS-8 [19], and the cut off 4. Values greater than or equal to 4 mean good quality of life. Detailed description of methods is described elsewhere [22]. The cohort's follow up continues and this report describes the preliminary findings.

2.2. Standard protocol approvals and patient consent

This study has been approved by the Helsinki University Hospital research ethics committee board, ID HUS/1493/2021 on 06-03-2021. All study participants sign written informed consent for participation. Protocol version (1.0) and trial registration data are available on the platform www.clinicaltrials.gov (NCT05699512).

2.3. Interventions at the rehabilitation clinic

Before the consultation, the patients underwent a range of blood

screening tests recommended in the Finnish national clinical guidelines for chronic fatigue [23]. Patients first met a doctor at the clinic, who assessed the medical history and performed clinical examination. If the clinician considered that the symptoms were due to another clinical or paraclinical abnormality, the patient was not included in the cohort but referred elsewhere.

At the consultation, the focus was on psychoeducation, which included giving information about the disease and its treatment and consulting the patient to empower them to overcome the disorder. To convince the patients, we sometimes recommended reading about recovered patients with long Covid at Recovery Norway [24]. The most important element was the listening encounter with the patients and offering hope. When the clinic started in 2021, there was no consensus on the nature of post-Covid-19 condition and no existing theoretical model to apply to psychoeducation. However, we sought information on the long-term symptoms of the previous SARS epidemics [25], and informed patients of the recovery observed in them. When the infographic by Saunders et al. presenting a biopsychosocial origin of post-Covid-19 condition became available [3], we used that to explain PCC to patients.

A multidisciplinary team supported the patient's treatment. All patients met with a physiotherapist, and a psychologist performed neuropsychological testing. Patients also could meet a social worker. The patients had an opportunity to attend group rehabilitation, which consisted of psychoeducation, relaxation exercises, and group discussions. For some patients, online therapies were suggested for managing insomnia, anxiety, or long-term physical symptoms, for example.

2.4. Statistical methods

We applied two-way agglomerative hierarchical clustering analysis with Euclidean distance and Ward linkage. Hierarchical clustering was chosen as it helps in identifying inherent patterns and structures within the data by grouping similar observations together. It also creates a visual representation of the relationships between data points through dendrogram plots. We checked the selection using the Elbow method but added one more cluster to have a more balanced analysis with clinically more meaningful clusters. In addition, the Gap statistic method suggested a larger optimal number of clusters.

We aimed at identifying both clusters of patients with similar symptom profiles as well as clusters of co-occurring symptoms (symptom clusters). Patients with missing baseline symptom data were excluded from the unsupervised clustering analysis. Of the 438 patients enrolled by October 2023 we were able to perform clustering on 409 because of missing data. The number of clusters for downstream analyses (symptom clusters) were determined based on inspection of the obtained dendrograms.

To ensure that the selected patients were representative of the overall study population, we compared the characteristics of the patients used in the cluster analysis with the characteristics of the patients with missing data using Chi-square tests for sex and Mann-Whitney-*U* tests for age. The baseline patient characteristics, comorbidities and PROMs were summarized for the overall population as well as by patient cluster.

Differences in baseline characteristics between patient clusters were studied using Kruskal-Wallis tests for continuous and Chi-squared tests for dichotomous variables. Changes in recovery, in terms of reaching EuroHIS-8 quality of life >4 , between baseline and each follow-up time point (3 months, 6 months and 12 months) were evaluated overall and for each cluster using paired samples *t*-test.

We performed multinomial logistic and linear regression analyses to determine factors that were associated with symptom clusters and changes in recovery. For logistic regression models we chose the relevant determinants from univariate analyses. With backward stepwise linear regression models we studied determinants from different classes of factors (age, sex, comorbidities, smoking, BMI, hospitalization,

anxiety, depression, antidepressants, employment, and living alone).

In all analyses, the level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$. The statistical analyses were carried out using R statistical computing environment version 4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2016. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>) R packages ggplot2 and kableExtra were used for visualization, pheatmap and dendextend were used for clustering.

3. Results

3.1. Study patient characteristics

In October 2023, the cohort had 409 patients enrolled of whom 70.4% were women. Most (91.0%) had been treated in outpatient care during acute Covid-19, 45 (9.0%) had been hospitalized and 18 (4.4%) had been in intensive care. All patients were PCR or antigen positive tested for Covid-19.

For clustering analyses, we used the information on all the 409 patients. On average, the patients were 44.8 years old, and 68.2% worked full-time or part-time. At baseline, the patients underwent a range of blood screening tests for chronic fatigue which were largely normal. Of the patients, 27% were obese (BMI over 30), and 34% overweight (BMI 25–29.9). The baseline characteristics of the study patients are presented in [Table 1](#).

At baseline, the patients reported on average 20.3 (SD 6.8) symptoms from the grid of 35 symptoms ([Table 1](#)). The prevalence of the 35 symptoms at baseline is presented in [Fig. 1](#). >80% of patients had fatigue, lack of energy, headache or dizziness, exhaustion in everyday activities, and concentration difficulties. Comorbidities were common in this patient population, mainly asthma, hypertension, depression, anxiety, and sleep apnea ([Table 1](#)).

3.2. Hierarchical clusters

Hierarchical cluster analysis divided the patients into three groups: Cluster-11 (17%), Cluster-17 (35%), and Cluster-25 (47%) according to the number of symptoms at baseline ([Fig. 2](#)). The cluster analysis also grouped patients with symptoms that occurred together. Fatigue and cognitive complaints were prevalent in all clusters ([Fig. 2](#), violet bars). The second symptom cluster included of pain, palpitations, hyperventilation, tingling in the limbs, and sleep disturbances. Emotion-related symptoms were prevalent in the third symptom cluster, and these symptoms were mainly present in Cluster-17 and Cluster-25. The fourth symptom cluster included mainly gastrointestinal symptoms. Clusters –17 and –25 typically had several overlapping symptoms.

Cluster-25 had multiple symptoms from all categories, and all had fatigue and cognitive complaints. Most patients in Cluster-17 also had fatigue and cognitive complaints, and many had in addition symptoms from the other symptom clusters. Cluster-11 had fewer symptoms, although fatigue and cognitive complaints were common.

3.3. Prognosis of symptoms and quality of life in follow up

We had follow-up information on 225 (55.0%), 210 (51.3%), and 153 patients (37.4%) at 3-, 6-, and 12-month follow-up, respectively. Older patients were more likely to answer our surveys. Otherwise, the responders and non-responders did not differ regarding sex, symptoms, quality of life, or work-status. Full information of responders and non-responders are presented in Supplementary material ([Table 5](#)).

Regardless of patient clusters, the mean number of symptoms decreased from 20.3 (SD 6.8) at baseline to 15.5 (SD 8) at 12 months. The frequency of symptoms was mainly the same as at baseline; however, joint pain had become more common ([Fig. 1](#), green bars).

The quality of life measured by EuroHIS improved in all patient clusters. At baseline, only 9% of patients had good quality of life as

Table 1

Participants' characteristics in the overall study population and by cluster.

	total	Cluster 11	Cluster 17	Cluster 25	p-value
Total (% of total)	409 (100.0)	71 (17.4)	143 (35.0)	195 (47.7)	
Female, N (%)	288 (70.4)	38 (53.5)	109 (76.2)	141 (72.3)	0.002
Age mean, years (SD)	44.8 (11.4)	45.0 (12.8)	46.5 (11.0)	43.5 (11.0)	0.03
Body mass index, mean, (SD) (kg/m ²)	27.5 (5.9)	27.0 (5.9)	26.9 (5.2)	28.1 (6.3)	0.20
Baseline 0–10 Functional ability mean (SD)	4.8 (2.0)	5.6 (2.0)	5.4 (1.9)	4.2 (2.0)	<
Baseline 0–10 Quality of life Mean (SD)	5.2 (2.1)	6.0 (2.0)	5.7 (2.0)	4.5 (2.0)	<
Symptom duration, years, mean (SD)	0.8 (0.5)	0.7 (0.4)	0.9 (0.5)	0.8 (0.6)	0.37
Number of comorbidities, mean (SD)	1.2 (1.5)	0.8 (1.3)	1.1 (1.5)	1.4 (1.6)	<
Number of symptoms, mean (SD)	20.3 (6.7)	11.5 (3.9)	17.5 (3.7)	25.5 (4.3)	<
Hospitalization during acute COVID-19 N (%)	37(9.0)	5(7.0)	15 (10.5)	17(8.7)	0.69
Intensive care unit during acute COVID-19 N (%)	18(4.4)	3(4.2)	8(5.6)	7(3.6)	0.65
At least one comorbidity N (%)	231 (56.5)	32 (45.1)	72 (50.3)	127 (65.1)	0.003
Employed N (%)	279 (68.2)	50 (70.4)	105 (73.4)	124 (63.6)	0.13
Tertiary education N (%)	232 (57.9)	41 (58.6)	78 (55.3)	113 (59.5)	0.75
Living alone, N (%)	111 (27.1)	23 (32.4)	32 (22.4)	56 (28.7)	0.22
Smoking, N (%)	28(6.9)	2(2.9)	10(7.2)	16(8.2)	0.34
Participated in at least one group therapy session at the clinic N (%)	93 (22.7)	12 (16.9)	37 (25.9)	44 (22.6)	0.34
Comorbidities confirmed from primary and secondary care patient registries:					
Asthma, N (%)	68 (16.6)	5(7.0)	22 (15.4)	41 (21.0)	0.03
Sleep apnea, N (%)	34(8.3)	3(4.2)	11(7.7)	20 (10.3)	0.24
Anxiety disorder, N (%)	42 (10.3)	3(4.2)	11(7.7)	28 (14.4)	0.03
Hypertension, N (%)	39(9.5)	8(11.3)	17 (11.9)	14(7.2)	0.29
Depression, N (%)	33(8.1)	5(7.0)	12(8.4)	16(8.2)	0.95
Hypothyroidism, N (%)	20(4.9)	6(8.5)	6(4.2)	8(4.1)	0.35
Diabetes, N (%)	16(3.9)	2(2.8)	6(4.2)	8(4.1)	0.90
Long-term insomnia, N (%)	26(6.4)	1(1.4)	8(5.6)	17(8.7)	0.09
Irritable bowel syndrome, N (%)	10(2.4)	0(0.0)	2(1.4)	8(4.1)	0.11
Fibromyalgia, N (%)	8(2.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	8(4.1)	0.01

measured by EuroHIS-8 while at 12 months, 33% of patients had good quality of life ([Table 2](#)). The quality of life improved in all patient clusters, regardless of the number of symptoms at baseline ([Table 2](#)).

3.4. Determinants associated with number of symptoms and recovery

[Table 3](#) presents the results of the multinomial logistic regression analysis. Female sex predicted belonging to Cluster-17 (OR 2.9, 95% CI 1.5–5.5) and to Cluster-25 (OR 2.2, 95% CI 1.2–3.9). In addition, more than one comorbidity determined more pronounced number of symptoms, in Cluster-17 (OR 2.7, 95% CI 1.1–6.7) and in Cluster-25 (OR 4.4, 95% CI 1.8–10.6).

To study the determinants of having symptoms belonging to the symptom clusters, we used linear regression models ([Table 4](#)). Female sex increased the number of cognitive, emotion-related, and

Fig. 1. Prevalence of the 35 symptoms at baseline ($n = 409$), and at 12 month follow-up ($n = 153$).

Fig. 2. Patient and symptom clusters in post Covid-19 ($n = 409$). The hierarchical cluster analysis grouped the patients according to the average number of symptoms to Cluster-25, Cluster-17 and Cluster-11. Symptom clusters were formed by the symptoms that appeared together in the patients. Red color represents presence of symptoms, blue color is absence of symptom. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2

Quality of life measured by EuroHIS at baseline and at 3-, 6-, and 12-month follow-up in the three clusters. EuroHIS greater than or equal to 4 means good quality of life.

	Month 0				Month 3				Month 6				Month 12			
	n	Mean (SD)	≥ 4, n (%)		n	Mean (SD); p value*	≥ 4, n (%)		n	Mean (SD); p value*	≥ 4, n (%)		n	Mean (SD); p value*	≥ 4, n (%)	
Cluster 11	71	3.4 (0.6)	12	(17)	41	3.6 (0.5) 0.10	14	(34)	37	3.8 (0.6) 0.004	16	(44)	25	4.1 (0.6) 0.002	17	(68)
Cluster 17	143	3.2 (0.6)	16	(11)	77	3.5 (0.7) 0.0 k2	23	(30)	70	3.5 (0.7) 0.007	18	(27)	54	3.6 (0.8) <0.001	19	(37)
Cluster 25	195	2.9 (0.5)	8	(4)	107	3.2 (0.7) <0.001	18	(17)	103	3.2 (0.7) <0.001	16	(16)	74	3.2 (0.7) <0.001	14	(19)
Total	409	3.1 (0.6)	36	(9)	225	3.4 (0.7) <0.001	55	(24)	210	3.4 (0.7) <0.001	50	(25)	153	3.5 (0.8) <0.001	50	(33)

SD denotes standard deviation.

* Paired samples *t*-test for comparison with baseline scores.

Table 3

Determinants associated with belonging to Cluster-17 or Cluster-25 following multivariate multinomial logistic regression (odds ratios).

Patient cluster	Cluster-11, Ref	Cluster-17		Cluster-25	
		OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI
(Intercept)	Ref	1.1	0.6–2.2	1.3	0.7–2.5
age > 55	Ref	0.9	0.4–1.8	0.8	0.4–1.6
age < 45	Ref	0.6	0.3–1.3	1.1	0.5–2.2
Female sex	Ref	2.9	1.5–5.5	2.2	1.2–3.9
1 Comorbidity	Ref	0.7	0.3–1.4	1.2	0.6–2.3
>1 Comorbidity	Ref	2.7	1.1–6.7	4.4	1.8–10.6

Description: Factors associated with symptom severity following multivariate multinomial logistic regression, presented as relative risk ratios. Statistically significant associated factors ($p \leq 0.05$) are italicized.

Abbreviations: *Ref*, reference category; *OR*, odds ratio; *CI*, confidence intervals.

gastrointestinal symptoms. Comorbidities were associated with the number of symptoms in the category of pain, trouble sleeping, palpitations and other symptoms, and gastrointestinal symptoms. Anxiety and using antidepressants were associated with fatigue and cognitive complaints. Fatigue, cognitive, and emotion-related symptoms were less common in those employed.

We ran the similar multinomial logistic regression analyses for prognosis, for reaching EuroHIS-8 quality of life >4. Hospitalization was associated with poorer recovery at 12 months. Otherwise, we did not observe differences between subgroups in recovery.

4. Discussion

This hierarchical cluster analysis divided the patients with post-Covid-19 condition into three clusters, with an average of 11, 17 or 25 symptoms of a list of 35 symptoms at baseline. Fatigue and cognitive complaints were typical in all clusters. In the one-year follow-up, the average number of symptoms decreased from 20.3 to 15.5, and the quality of life improved, regardless of the number of symptoms at baseline in this cohort of tertiary care patients with post-Covid-19 condition.

We studied with multinomial logistic and linear regression models the factors that determined the subgroups. Female sex and more than one comorbidity were the significant determinants of belonging to the clusters with more symptoms, Cluster-17 and Cluster-25. For symptom clusters, in addition to female sex and comorbidities, anxiety, use of antidepressants, BMI, and smoking were among determinants of the symptom clusters. The number of determinants of symptoms may reflect the probable biopsychosocial origins of the post-Covid-19 condition [3,16,17]. Female sex and emotional stress are among well-known determinants of functional disorders [20,26].

We observed four different symptom clusters that often overlapped.

All patient clusters had fatigue and cognitive complaints, lack of energy, headache, exhaustion from everyday activities, and memory problems. Another common symptom cluster was the category of pain, trouble sleeping, palpitations and other symptoms. We also observed a symptom cluster with emotion-related symptoms, and a fourth one with mainly gastrointestinal symptoms.

Other post-Covid-19 condition hierarchical cluster studies have also typically divided patients into three groups based on the severity of symptoms [9–11,14,27]. The symptom clusters found in these studies differ, although there are similarities. Like our study, Frontera et al. identified a symptom cluster characterized by mood symptoms [10]. Cardiovascular symptoms typical of dysautonomia were present in Frontera et al. and Kenny et al. studies [10,11]. A study from Spain showed that preexisting medical conditions and socioeconomic factors are associated with long Covid [28].

A recent systematic review by Kuodi et al. [14] stated that studies reporting PCC symptom clusters are rare as many studies report only individual symptoms. The Kuodi review does not report whether the included studies were hospitalized in acute Covid-19 or not. There is a potential selection bias in PCC studies towards hospitalized patients, which cover <1% of all Covid-19 sufferers. This may cause a grimmer picture of the prognosis and increase worry among patients [29]. The comorbidities most likely have more effect in the hospitalized patients than in other patients with post-Covid-19 condition.

Our intervention consisted typically of one or two appointments with a physician, a physiotherapist, and a psychologist. Only 22.7% of patients attended the group intervention, which had six sessions. Reasons for this were that the patients did not feel need for the group intervention or had logistical problems. Our clinical conclusion is that an important element in the therapy was listening to the patient, taking the symptoms seriously, alleviating them with the usual means: psycho-education, relaxation exercises, sometimes with chronic pain drugs and betablockers. However, the most important factor was offering the patients hope of recovery.

In the Dutch population-based Lifelines cohort, 21.4% Covid-19-positive participants versus 8.7% Covid-19-negative controls had at least one of the core symptoms. Hence, 12.7% of symptoms could be attributed to Covid-19. In our cohort, we cannot estimate what part of the symptoms were due to other reasons and comorbidities. The patients in our cohort often had asthma, depression, anxiety, and sleep apnea, which can cause similar symptoms as the post-viral syndrome. Comorbidities were a significant determinant in the multinomial logistic regression analysis, and they speak for the complex and multifactorial etiology of post-Covid-19 condition.

Our study is one of the first PCC cluster analysis to report patient prognosis. The previous post-Covid-19 prognosis studies have reported on patients who were hospitalized in the acute phase, and the in this patient group, the symptoms often continued at 2-years follow up

5. Conclusions

The prognosis of tertiary care patients with post-Covid-19 condition seems favorable, regardless of the quantity of the symptoms. The number of symptoms decreased in all clinical clusters and quality of life improved. Groups of fatigue and cognitive complaints, emotion-related, gastrointestinal, and pain, trouble sleeping, palpitations and other symptoms stand out from the spectrum as symptom clusters. Female sex, more than one comorbidity, BMI, smoking, and mental-health related variables (anxiety and use of antidepressants) predicted higher symptom burden, suggesting multifactorial origins of PCC.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Helena Liira: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Paul Garner:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Antti Malmivaara:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Mari Kanerva:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Kirsi Kvarnström:** Resources, Project administration. **Markku Sainio:** Writing – original draft. **Mikko Varonen:** Statistical analyses, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Mikko Venäläinen:** Supervision, Methodology. **Aki Vuokko:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Jari Arokoski:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

Helena Liira and Markku Sainio have received honorariums for lectures and workshops about functional disorders and post-Covid-19 condition. The remaining authors declare no conflicts of interest relating to this manuscript.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychores.2024.111808>.

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